

CAP 2028-2034: Navigating change for an evidence-based policy

ABSTRACT

The new Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) proposals introduce a dedicated regulation for the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), integrating with the newly established National and Regional Partnership Fund (NRPF). In the proposed post-2027 CAP, agricultural spending would be delivered as the “CAP chapter” within National and Regional Partnership Plans (NRPPs). Under these new proposals, the design of the NRPPs, including the design of future agricultural policies, does not prescribe a detailed sequence of steps, such as stakeholder consultation, needs assessment and prioritisation, SWOT analysis, intervention logic, and ex-ante evaluation. This fundamental shift, as envisaged in the Commission’s proposals, presents significant challenges for both national and EU policymakers.

While Member States have been granted greater flexibility, mechanisms to ensure evidence-based policy and coherence across Member States in delivering EU objectives are no longer adequately addressed. This gap may undermine the quality of strategic planning in the agricultural chapter. National managing authorities risk selectively adopting scientific results and methodologies that reinforce their own perspectives (i.e., positive reinforcement bias). To counter this, an integrated research approach is essential, where robust and different complementary methodologies – both qualitative and quantitative – are used across different scales and geographical contexts.

1. Introduction

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) has long been one of the EU’s most significant and visible policies, both in terms of budgetary weight and its impact on farmers, rural communities, food systems, and environmental sustainability. In July 2025, the European Commission presented its proposals for the next EU budget (Multiannual Financial Framework - MFF) and a restructured CAP for the period 2028-2034. One of the major changes is that the CAP has been integrated into a single fund, the National and Regional Partnership Fund (NRPF), bringing together all EU funds under shared management between the Commission and the Member States, such as the Cohesion Policy and the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund, into one overarching structure. The proposals are both ambitious and controversial, and, for the CAP in particular, they would imply significant changes, such as in the area of governance and performance framework.

This reform aims to streamline management, enhance flexibility, and strengthen performance-based governance. However, it also raises important and contentious questions: What do the proposed reforms mean in practice for policymakers at both the EU and Member State levels? How will they affect agricultural policy design, monitoring, and evaluation? How might they reshape the process of evidence-based policymaking? What are the implications for evidence-based policymaking, and what insights will be required from researchers who analyse this process?

While the final details of the future CAP will depend on the outcome of negotiations between the co-legislators (the Council and the European Parliament), this Tools4CAP policy brief offers an initial exploration of the proposals' implications. It is structured in three parts. First, it provides a concise overview of the Commission's proposals for the MFF and the CAP. Second, it provides an assessment of accompanying key challenges to ensure that NRPPs are properly designed and monitored. Finally, it makes key recommendations for EU and national policymakers and researchers to strengthen evidence-based decision-making.

The overarching aim of this brief is to guide policymakers through the evolving CAP landscape and to outline how the research community can best support policymakers and the wider stakeholder community to facilitate evidence-based decision-making in this changing context.

2. CAP reform: Budget, interventions and governance

The proposed new MFF has an indicated €2 trillion budget, significantly larger than under the current programme. The basis for the enlarged budget would be to allow the MFF to better address the wider range of challenges the EU now faces. The proposed MFF is split across the following funds:

Overview of the main funds and their distribution within the proposed Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF).

2.1. A Smaller CAP Budget?

A fundamental change proposed by the European Commission involves integrating the CAP into a single financial instrument, the NRPF. The NRPF is designed to support activities such as cohesion and agriculture, described as the “pillars of European solidarity.” This proposal has raised concerns and sparked debate over the future visibility and autonomy of agricultural policy, whether the overall CAP budget will remain stable and whether such integration could lead to further “renationalisation” of agricultural policy, thereby undermining the ‘common’ European character of the CAP. At present, it remains impossible to determine the overall total budget that will ultimately be available for the future CAP.

Three key factors contribute to this uncertainty. Firstly, part of the budget is not earmarked for specific spending. Therefore, the allocation of this ‘unearmarked’ budget will be subject to competition among the various policy areas covered by the fund. Indeed, while €294 billion has been ring-fenced for CAP income

support interventions, €237 billion remains unallocated to any specific policy area, although the relative share of this non-allocated amount varies greatly across Member States. Secondly, numerous provisions have been introduced to address potential future crises, meaning that the planned budget may not reflect actual expenditure by the end of the next programming period. For instance, 25% of the “unearmarked” funds are set aside and may be directed towards unforeseen expenditures arising from crisis situations due to natural disasters, either to the CAP or to the other objectives of the Fund. The Commission has also introduced a Union safety net, allocating €6.3 billion to address market crises in the agricultural sector. Thirdly, assessing the total CAP budget envelope is particularly challenging due to the introduction of revised co-financing rules. Under the current programming period, only interventions financed by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development are subject to co-financing. In contrast, under the proposed system, only four specific interventions will be fully financed by the EU budget. All other forms of support will require national co-financing at different rates. The combined effect of these reforms is an ambiguous budgetary provision for the future CAP.

2.2. Changes in Interventions

A notable innovation in the proposed CAP framework is the **broader and more flexible definition of income support**, which now encompasses not only area-based payments, but also measures such as agri-environmental and climate actions and targeted support for young farmers. While the aggregate value of all income support interventions is ring-fenced, it is important to note that not all such interventions are fully financed by the EU budget. In fact, only degressive area-based income support, coupled income support, crop-specific payments for cotton, and the small farmers’ scheme remain exempt from national co-financing requirements. While this integrated approach reflects an effort to streamline interventions, it also changes established implementation procedures and the existing financial framework, thereby introducing new financial and administrative requirements for Member States.

The new policy framework also introduces stronger **degressivity and capping** conditions by reducing payments to larger farms and redirecting resources towards smaller holdings. In principle, this reform aims to enhance fairness in the allocation of support and to better promote generational renewal.

Finally, the current CAP introduced “enhanced conditionality” to elevate the baseline requirement for sustainability actions, reflecting the social contract whereby farmers receive income support in exchange for adherence to EU standards on the environment, animal welfare, and public health. In a contrasting move, the new Commission proposal would abolish the long-established General Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAECs). These will be replaced by a new concept of **farm stewardship**, granting Member States even greater autonomy to design context-specific farming practices and shifting the emphasis from compliance-based conditions to incentive-based approaches.

2.3. Broader Participation in Policy-Making?

As in the current programming period, the responsibility for defining the CAP's different interventions lies within the competent authority in the Member States, who are tasked with developing national plans. However, a significant departure from the previous approach is that the new NRPPs encompass all policy domains addressed by the NRPF, rather than focusing solely on the agricultural sector. Consequently, Member States are now not only responsible for drafting the operational details of the CAP, but also for determining the allocation of the unearmarked budget of the NRPF across various policy areas. This devolution inevitably brings new stakeholders into the decision-making process, potentially challenging established policy choices concerning the CAP. Thus, governance is fundamentally shifting further from a predominantly EU-centred model to one with an increasingly national focus, yet also multi-sectoral and partnership-based in nature. While this approach may strengthen policy coherence and integration, it also places agricultural priorities within broader national exchequer priorities. The inclusion of multiple

ministries and policy fields may make it harder to maintain a clear strategic vision for rural areas and farming communities.

The European Commission's role is also evolving. Instead of prescribing a planning process, as in the 2023-2027 CAP cycle, it will now provide CAP national strategic recommendations at the outset of the planning process, providing tailored guidance to each Member State. Member States are expected to address a substantial proportion of these recommendations within their respective NRPPs. Subsequently, the Commission will assess the submitted plans for compliance and coherence and, where justified, may request further information or modifications.

In contrast to the previous CAP Strategic Plan process, where the Commission prescribed a detailed sequence of steps, including stakeholder consultation, needs assessment and prioritisation, SWOT analysis, intervention logic, and ex-ante evaluation, Member States now enjoy greater autonomy. However, it also places a heavier responsibility on Member States to demonstrate the quality and transparency of national-level policymaking. The current regulations do not specify the methodologies or tools to be employed in the design of NRPPs, granting Member States considerable discretion in their approach. Without clearly defined methodologies for each step, the consistency and robustness of evidence-based policy design may vary widely between Member States.

Nevertheless, Member States are required to organise and implement a comprehensive partnership process, ensuring balanced representation of diverse stakeholders. This includes, but is not limited to, rural representatives, civil society organisations, other relevant bodies, and research institutions across multiple policy domains. This expansion presents both an opportunity and a risk. It can democratise policy development, facilitating the provision of rural perspectives and a broader, cross-sectoral dialogue. Yet, without clear guidance, there is a danger that less-organised and under-resourced groups, particularly those in remote rural areas, may be overshadowed by more agile and influential institutional actors. To ensure meaningful participation, Member States will need to establish transparent consultation processes, feedback mechanisms, and simple digital tools to document stakeholder inputs and trace how they inform policy choices.

One might argue that the strategic orientation of the CAP, previously driven by a set of specific objectives and corresponding interventions, has now been subsumed within a broader political discourse. Alternatively, it could be contended that policy decisions will need to be substantiated with robust evidence to withstand heightened scrutiny. In either case, it will demand significant resources from the European Commission to ensure that Member States fulfil Union objectives and resources from Member States to address the needs of all constituencies, including rural areas, which are often less organised and less well-resourced and therefore less able to make their voices heard.

It is important to note that these decisions will be made within the context of the new horizontal regulation, which establishes the overarching rules and performance framework for the MFF, to which the CAP is also subject. The performance framework retains the logic of linking intervention fields to output and result indicators. However, two notable changes are apparent. Firstly, intervention fields are now associated with coefficients that reflect, a priori, their anticipated contribution to Union cross-cutting objectives, introducing a more formulaic, but less adaptive evaluation system. Secondly, impact and context indicators, which are essential for evaluating the effectiveness and efficiency of regulation, are no longer included in the proposed framework, although it is possible they may be added later. These changes may weaken the analytical basis for performance evaluation and reduce accountability, especially if Member States diverge in their data collection and monitoring practices. Accordingly, while Tools4CAP welcomes the possibility that the Commission may subsequently introduce impact indicators, embedding measurable and substantive impact indicators at the core of the policy design, and ensuring that they are linked to well-defined causal pathways, would strengthen both the comparability and the validity of the overall framework. Stronger coordination among the Commission, Member States and the research community will be vital to ensure that policy performance remains transparent and comparable across the Union.

The current situation surrounding the CAP 2028-2034 bears some resemblance to the Agenda 2000 reforms, which were implemented prior to the accession of the EU-13 Member States and marked a pivotal shift toward loosening central control and enhancing governance at the Member State level. The proposed policy changes seem to be not only a natural evolution, building on past policy directions, but also a strategic preparation for potential future enlargement, with their legacy and impact intended to remain enduring features of the upcoming EU agricultural policy.

3. Main Challenges to Designing an Evidence-Based Future CAP

Budgetary Uncertainty and Fragmentation

The integration of the CAP into the NRPF introduces significant uncertainty regarding the final budget envelope for agriculture. While a portion of the CAP budget is ring-fenced, a substantial share remains flexible and subject to competition from other policy areas. This makes it challenging to accurately predict the actual resources available for agricultural interventions during the programming period. The introduction of new crisis provisions, the increased room for amendments of the NRPPs, and a Union safety net further complicate long-term planning and evidence-based prioritisation, as planned allocations may not reflect actual expenditure.

Complexity and Disincentives in Co-Financing Arrangements

The revised co-financing rules represent a marked departure from previous frameworks. This creates a complex landscape in which the attractiveness of certain interventions is diminished, especially in Member States with more limited financial capacity. There is a risk that interventions with a high impact over the longer term may be deprioritised in favour of those that create a lower burden on national exchequer budgets, undermining the overall effectiveness of the CAP and potentially leading to underinvestment in rural development and environmental objectives.

For instance, whereas the current eco-schemes do not necessitate national co-financing, agri-environmental and climate measures (AECMs) require only a 20% national contribution, the proposed increase to a 30% co-financing rate for agri-environmental and climate actions is likely to render these interventions less attractive to Member States. Any funds added to the ring-fenced amount from the non-allocated portion of the NRPF will require the appropriate standard regional contribution rates of up to 60% (Art. 20(4)).

In the current programming period, CAP regulations were relatively prescriptive, specifying the tools to be used and requiring Member States to undertake stakeholder consultation, needs assessment, SWOT analysis, intervention logic, and ex-ante evaluation. Given the Commission's CAP proposals would provide greater Member State autonomy in the design of some measures, there is a risk of reducing the overall quality of evidence-based policy, unless the potential impacts of new measures are rigorously interrogated by researchers and policymakers. The absence of a clear intervention logic and the weakening of links between objectives, interventions, and results, further undermine the capacity for robust evaluation.

Diverse Impacts of Degressivity and Capping

Given the heterogeneous nature of farm structures, both within and between Member States, the introduction of stronger degressivity and capping measures will have highly variable effects across the Union. Those Member States with a historical prevalence of small farms may find themselves with limited scope to reallocate resources, potentially constraining their policy options. Conversely, Member States with more concentrated land ownership may experience substantial budget reallocation and heightened political sensitivity. These Member State differences highlight the need for rigorous national impact assessments, using harmonised indicators and simulation tools, to ensure that redistribution mechanisms achieve their intended social and economic objectives without generating unintended effects.

Ambiguity and Inconsistency in Farm Stewardship

The concept of farm stewardship is more vague and less prescriptive than the GAEC concept, which has been in use for more than 20 years. Whereas GAECs provided a transparent and relatively uniform set of EU standards for farmer compliance, farm stewardship allows Member States greater autonomy to design context-specific practices. While this may encourage innovation and local adaptation, it also introduces a risk of inconsistent interpretation and implementation across the Union. The absence of common rules increases the potential for divergence in the level and nature of support provided, with significant implications for maintaining a level playing field within the Single Market. Without robust EU-level mechanisms to ensure a level playing field, the 'common' characteristic of the CAP is at risk.

Balancing Economic, Societal and Environmental objectives

The proposals include enhanced support for young farmers and measures to facilitate the transition towards more sustainable production practices, both of which are intended to promote generational renewal and a more competitive, environmentally compliant agricultural sector. However, the increased flexibility for Member States may have the unintended effect of perpetuating existing production patterns and delaying necessary structural change. There is a risk that, rather than fostering innovation and renewal, these provisions could reinforce the status quo, thereby undermining the long-term objectives of improving competitiveness and sustainability.

Analytical and Administrative Capacity

The new proposal from the European Commission places substantial demands on both the European Commission and Member States. Ensuring that all relevant needs, including those of rural areas and less organised stakeholder groups, are addressed in an evidence-based manner will require significant analytical and administrative resources. While *ex ante* evaluations are no longer required, the European Commission has placed greater emphasis on interim and *ex post* evaluations, particularly on the use of specific methodological tools such as counterfactual approaches and experimental designs. There is a risk that, in the absence of clear guidance and sufficient capacity, policy decisions may be driven more by political considerations and lobbying rather than by empirical evidence.

4. Recommendation for Policy makers

4.1. Recommendations for the European Commission and Co-Legislators

1. Promote Evidence-Based and Inclusive Policy Design

- Strengthen mechanisms for evidence-based policymaking by prioritising data and scientific facts, selecting interventions that provide the best policy mix, and emphasising a results-based approach based on policy indicators that actually show the achievement of set goals, as well as impact assessment in line with the Better Regulation Guidelines.
- Ensure that the design and evaluation of NRPPs and CAP chapters are developed in a realistic timetable and underpinned by transparent, harmonised templates and guidance, including clear definitions of roles and responsibilities for all actors involved, while providing timely guidance and capacity-building support to Member States.

2. Ensure Rigorous Analysis and Accountability

- Promote balanced stakeholder representation and a partnership-based stakeholder engagement process, and also ensure that the stakeholder engagement process itself is subject to meaningful evaluation.

- Foster interdisciplinary and cross-country research and knowledge-transfer collaboration to share best practice, methodological innovations, policy evidence and lessons learned, thereby strengthening the evidence base for future CAP reform.

3. Maintain Policy Coherence and Financial Responsibility

- Maintain robust EU-level oversight by defining a clear approval process in the proposed regulation to prevent the “renationalisation” of agricultural policy and to guarantee a level playing field across Member States, particularly in the context of increased flexibility and subsidiarity.
- Take advantage of the new proposals on data interoperability (Performance Regulation Art. 58 and Annex XVI, which require automatic synchronisation and submission of data between Member States and the Commission) and the Single Gateway (Performance Regulation Art. 12), which should increase accessibility to relevant data for researchers.

4.2. Recommendations for Member States

1. Promote Evidence-Based and Inclusive Policy Design

- Organise the NRPP design process to ensure balanced representation of all relevant stakeholders, including rural representatives, civil society, research organisations, and sectoral experts, in line with the principles of partnership and multi-level governance. This should be underpinned by simple tracking tools for all parties involved to follow progress and understand how their input contributes to changes in the drafting process of the NRPPs.
- Establish interministerial working groups or external process moderators to foster cross-sectoral collaboration and ensure that the needs of rural areas and less-organised groups are adequately reflected.
- Support and coordinate a research agenda dedicated to improving the strategic planning of the CAP.

2. Ensure Rigorous Analysis and Accountability

- Ensure that priority-setting is grounded in evidence, informed by robust research, and conducted through a broadly participatory process involving all segments of society. This should be based on a systematic assessment of existing policies and on the identification of the most appropriate policy mix and results-oriented interventions. It should also include the selection of indicators that, within a clear intervention logic, allow for the monitoring of progress towards ambitious objectives while taking into account the resources available.
- Monitor the implications of degressivity, capping, and co-financing arrangements for different farm structures and regions, and conduct regular impact assessments to inform policy adjustments.

3. Maintain Policy Coherence and Financial Responsibility

- Safeguard regional autonomy and accountability, and avoid recentralisation that could weaken democratic oversight or responsiveness to local needs.
- Ensure that national contributions are efficiently managed and that the efficiency and effectiveness of public spending are regularly reviewed.

5. Implications for researchers

For researchers and the academic community dealing with multi-sectoral and diverse scientific fields, the current transition presents both a challenge and an opportunity to support evidence-based policymaking. There is a pressing need to address budgetary data gaps, enable like-for-like comparisons across Member States and programming periods, and evaluate the impact of reforms such as degressivity, capping, and changes in farm structure. Researchers should develop and apply integrated methodologies, combining qualitative and quantitative approaches at multiple scales and in diverse geographical contexts, to support robust policy evaluation. Independent, critical analysis of NRPPs and CAP chapters is vital, with particular attention to the effectiveness of farm stewardship, income distribution, and the achievement of social, climate, and environmental objectives.

The academic community should engage proactively with policymakers to ensure that research findings inform the design, implementation, and revision of interventions, and that policy decisions are substantiated by robust empirical evidence. It is also important to advocate for the explicit use of SMART objectives and intervention logic in policy design and evaluation, in line with the European Commission's Better Regulation Guidelines. By contributing to the development of standardised templates, indicators, and evaluation frameworks, and by fostering interdisciplinary and cross-country collaboration, researchers can help to ensure transparency, comparability, and accountability in CAP and NRPP implementation, thereby strengthening the evidence base for future CAP.

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